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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Pack

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ABSTRACT

Herbal cosmetics have gained significant importance due to their safety, efficacy, and minimal side effects compared to synthetic products. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal face pack using natural ingredients such as Multani mitti, Turmeric, Sandalwood, Aloe vera, Neem, Nutmeg, Sweet potato, and Rose water. These ingredients are known for their cleansing, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and skin-nourishing properties. The face pack was prepared by mixing all ingredients in appropriate proportions and evaluated for various parameters such as organoleptic properties, pH, particle size, washability, skin irritation, and stability. The results indicated that the formulation was stable, safe, and suitable for topical application. Thus, the prepared herbal face pack can be used as an effective skincare product.[1][2]

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are defined as the products used for the purposes of cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or alternating the appearance.^[3] In ayurveda, the herbal paste is called as “mukha lepa” used for as a facial therapy. This herbal paste smeared on face to treat acne, pimple, scars, marks and pigments.^[4] A face pack is a smooth, powdery substance that is applied to the face and a proper herbal face pack should deliver necessary nutrients

to your skin as well as penetrate the subcutaneous layer to deliver needed nutrients. Ayurvedic face packs are different kind of herbal face packs that improve wrinkles, pimples, acne, and dark spots on the skin. Also, it increases fairness and smoothness of the skin.^[5]

Typically, a mix of ingredients that can be applied either as a paste or a mask, a face pack is designed to cleanse, nourish or rejuvenate skin. Face packs play an important role in the maintenance of facial

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skin by eliminating dead skin cells, excessive oil and other impurities while acting as therapeutic agents (e.g. anti-acne, anti-inflammatory and skin-whitening) for the face. The present study aims to formulate a herbal face pack using a combination of these natural ingredients and to evaluate its physicochemical characteristics and overall effectiveness. The evaluation includes tests for parameters such as texture, pH, color, spreadability, stability, irritancy, and user acceptability, to ensure the product is both effective and safe for regular use.

Traditional systems (Ayurvedic and herbal) of using natural materials for skincare like Multani mitti (Fuller's Earth), Neem (Azadirachta Indica), Turmeric (Curcuma Longa), Sandalwood (Santalum Album), and Rose Petals (Rosa Indica) have been historically suggested. Each of these natural ingredients has been clinically established as having antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, astringent, cooling and skin-toning properties.^[6]

1.1 Benefits of Applying Face Pack:-^[7,8]

- Face packs usually remove dead cells of skin.
- These face masks provide a soothing and relaxing effect on skin.
- Regular use of natural face masks bring glow to skin, improve skin texture and complexion.
- Natural face packs make the skin look young and healthy.
- They help to restore the lost shine and glow of skin in short span of time.
- They help to prevent premature aging of skin.
- Formation of wrinkles, fine lines and sagging of skin can be effectively controlled by using natural face packs.

1.2 Precautions to be Taken While Applying Face Pack:-^[7]

- Select the face pack according to your skin type. Take opinion of natural therapist or concerned skin expert before applying face pack.
- The face pack should not be left on face more than 15 to 20 minutes. Keeping for very long time may result in formation of wrinkles, sagging of skin and enlargement of open pores.
- Apply face pack once in a week.
- Don't try to peel or scratch the dried face pack. This may harm underlying skin. Spray water (which is at room temperature) on face before removing dried face pack. After removing the mask, roll an ice cube on facial skin. This helps to close open pores and tightens skin. It also tones and soothes the skin.
- Do not scrub face vigorously. This may result in eruption of pimples and dark spots.
- Stay away from heat when you have applied face pack.
- Avoid applying face pack near "eye zone". The skin around eye is very delicate. The process of removing face pack may damage the sensitive skin around eyes.

2. PLAN OF WORK: -

3. AIM AND OBJECTIVES: -

AIM: -

Formulation and evaluation of herbal face pack.

OBJECTIVE: -

- Ideal properties of face pack:
 - It should be non-irritating and non-toxic.
 - It should be stable both physically and chemically.
 - It should be free from gritty particles.
 - It should have pleasant odour.
 - They should be capable of producing significant cleaning of the skin.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW: -

Table 4.1 Literature Review

Sr.no	Title of the article	Author	Results obtained from literature
1)	Formulation and evaluation of herbal face pack	Sharma et al.,2019	Reported that herbal face packs improve skin texture and reduce acne due to natural ingredients.
2)	Evaluation of herbal cosmetic preparations	Patel & patel,2020	Concluded that herbal cosmetics are safe, effective, and show minimal side effects.
3)	Role of turmeric in skin care	Kumar et al.,2018	Found turmeric has strong anti- inflammatory and anti-bacterial properties useful for skin treatment.
4)	Neem as a Medicinal Plant in Dermatology	Singh et al., 2021	Demonstrated neem has antimicrobial activity effective against acne-causing bacteria.
5)	Aloe Vera in Cosmetic Applications	Verma et al., 2017	Reported aloe vera provides hydration and promotes skin healing.
6)	Application of Multani Mitti in Skin Care	Joshi et al., 2022	Found Multani mitti acts as an oil absorber and deep cleanser.
7)	Sandalwood and its Cosmetic Benefits	Khan et al., 2019	Reported sandalwood has cooling, soothing, and anti-aging properties.
8)	Reported sandalwood has cooling, soothing, and anti-aging properties.	Desai et al., 2021	Showed good stability, pH balance, and skin compatibility of herbal face packs.
9)	Natural Cosmetic Formulations	Rani et al., 2018	Found herbal products reduce side effects compared to synthetic cosmetics.
10)	Antioxidant Activity of Herbal Products	Yadav et al., 2019	Demonstrated herbal ingredients provide antioxidant protection for skin.
11)	Herbal Powder Formulations for Skin	Patel et al., 2021	Reported good spreadability and stability in powder formulations.
12)	Cosmetic Evaluation of Herbal Products	Mehta et al., 2020	Found herbal cosmetics have good user acceptability and safety.

5. MATERIALS AND METHOD: -

The materials used in the present purchased from local market, powdered for further use. The below are the details of the plant materials study. The details of the plant material used for the formulation of face pack are mentioned below.^[9]

5.1 Multani Mitti (Calcium bentonite):-

- Scientific Name:- Fuller's Earth.
- Biological Source: It is a natural clay composed mainly of hydrated aluminum silicates with variable amounts of magnesium, calcium, and iron.
- Uses:
 1. Used in face packs for its oil-absorbing and cleansing properties.
 2. Helps in removing impurities, dead skin cells, and excess sebum from the skin.
 3. Has a cooling effect on the skin and is often used to treat acne, pimples, and blemishes.
 4. Improves skin tone and blood circulation.
 5. Sometimes used as a hair cleanser or scalp treatment for oily hair and dandruff.^[10]
- Multani mitti helps skin by different ways like diminishing pore sizes, removing blackheads and whiteheads fading freckles, soothing sunburns, cleansing skin, improving blood circulation, complexion, reducing acne and blemishes and gives a glowing effect to a skin as they contain healthy nutrients.
- Multani mitti is rich magnesium chloride.^[9]

Figure 5.1. Multani Mitti

5.2 Turmeric (Curuma longa):-

- Synonym: Haldi , Indian Saffron
- Biological Source: - It consists of the dried rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* Linn.
- Family: Zingiberaceae (Ginger family)
- Uses:
 1. Acts as a natural antiseptic and antibacterial agent helpful in treating wounds and skin infections.
 2. Has strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.
 3. Commonly used in herbal face packs for improving skin complexion, reducing acne, and soothing inflammation.
 4. Helps reduce hyper pigmentation, dark spots, and gives skin a natural glow.
 5. Also used internally for boosting immunity, aiding digestion, inflammation.^[11]
- Haridra has anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic activity. It is best blood purifier and helps in wound healing. It possesses best

blood purification action so it is used in all disease with blood impurities origin.^[12]

Figure 5.2. turmeric powder

5.3 Sandal wood (*Santalum alba*)

- Synonym: Chandan, White Sandalwood
- Biological Source: - It is obtained from the heartwood of *Santalum album* Linn.
- Family: Santalaceae
- Uses:
 1. Known for its cooling, soothing, and anti-inflammatory properties.
 2. Used in herbal face packs to reduce acne, blemishes, and skin irritation.
 3. Helps in brightening the skin tone and gives a natural glow
 4. Acts as a natural astringent, tightening the skin and reducing oiliness.
 5. Its aromatic nature makes it a common ingredient in perfumes and cosmetic products.
 6. Also used in Ayurvedic medicine for treating skin diseases, headaches, and fever.^[13]

Figure 5.3. sandalwood powder

5.4 Aloe Vera (*Aloe barbadensis*)

Synonym: -*Aloe barbadense*

Family: -Liliaceae

Aloe vera is well known for its anti-inflammatory, skin protection, anti-fungal, anti-viral, antiseptic, and wound healing properties.

Aloe vera has anti-microbial property rendering it ideal to deal with acne and pimples. Aloe vera is a great moisturizer intended for a skin. Aloe vera powder contains several nutrients like glycerin, sodium palmate, sodium carbonate, sodium palm kemelate, sorbitol.^[14]

Figure 5.4. Aloe vera gel

5.5 Nutmeg: -

- Synonyms: -*Semen myristicae*,
- Source: -*Myristica fragrans*
- Family: -*Myristicaceae*.

- Nutmeg has antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, making it a great addition to your skincare arsenal. It keeps your skin healthy, smooth, and supple. Nutmeg's benefits include acne and eradicating blackheads. Nutmeg contains potent anti-inflammatory plant compounds that act as anti-oxidants. Nutmeg is a mild exfoliant that will help to eliminate dead skin cells, resulting in smoother, brighter skin. It is commonly used in face masks and scrubs, and it can help to reduce the appearance of fine lines, wrinkles, and uneven skin tone.

Figure 5.5. Nutmeg powder

5.6 Sweet potato: -

- Family: -Convolvulacea
- Sweet potato has been a staple food in many parts of the world. Sweet potatoes are a rich source of vitamin a, vitamin c, and antioxidants. Vitamin c and vitamin e are essential for skin and hair health. which is the skin's primary structural protein. Vitamin c has anti-inflammatory properties, according to a number of studies. The vitamin also helps with the treatment of skin disorders such as acne. In the morning glory family, they are naturally sweet roots. Sweet potatoes are a great source of water, keeping your skin hydrated. Proper hydration is vital to maintaining skin health because it reduces

dryness, flakiness, and the formation of fine lines.

Figure 5.6. sweet potato flour

5.7 Neem Powder: -

- Synonym: Margosa, Indian Lilac, Neem Patta Churna
- Biological Source: It is obtained from the dried leaves of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.
- Family: Meliaceae
- Uses:
 1. Has strong antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory properties—effective in treating acne, pimples, and skin infections
 2. Used in herbal face packs to purify the skin, control excess oil, and prevent breakouts
 3. Helps in healing wounds, reducing itchiness, and soothing irritated skin
 4. Acts as a natural detoxifier making the skin clearer and healthier.
 5. Also used in treating dandruff, scalp infections, and as an ingredient in oral care products^[15]

Figure 5.7 neem powder

5.8 Rose:-

- Family: -Rosaceae
- Synonyms: -Hulthemia Dumort.
- Rose is mainly used for medicinal and commercial purposes. Due to its anti-inflammatory, aphrodisiac, anti-depressant,

Figure 5.8 rose water

6. FORMULATON: -

Table 6.1 Formulation table

Sr. No	Ingredient	Scientific Name	F1 (Qty in gm)	F2 (Qty in gm)	F3 (Qty in gm)	F4 (Qty in gm)	F5 (Qty in gm)	F6 (Qty in gm)
1.	Multani mitti	Calcium bentonite	17	18	19	17	15	15
2.	Turmeric powder	Curcuma longa	1	2	1	3	2	3
3.	Sandalwood	Santalum album	5	3	2	2	4	4
4.	Aloe vera	Aloe barbadensis	3	4	3	3	5	4
5.	Nutmeg	Myristica fragrans	1	2	3	3	4	3
6.	Sweet potato	Lpomoea batatas	15	13	15	14	15	14
7.	Neem	Azadirachta indica	2	3	4	4	3	3
8.	Rose water	Hulthemia dumort	6	5	3	4	2	4

6.1 METHOD OF PREPARATION: -

- 1) All the required herbal powders for the face pack preparation were accurately Weighed individually by using digital balance.^[1]
- 2) The herbal drugs such as Aloe vera, sweet potato powder, Rose water, Neem powder, were transferred to mortar and pestle and triturated.^[17]
- 3) Herbal drugs such as Multani Mitti, Sandal Wood, Turmeric, & Nutmeg powder were triturated in a separate mortar and Pestle to form uniform fine mixture.^[18]
- 4) All the ingredients were combined according to the formula.^[19]
- 5) Previously prepared mixture of herbal powders was transferred to the mixture of fine

Powders and triturated to obtain uniform drug powder of face pack.

- 6) The mixture was passed through sieve no. 120 to ensure uniform particle size.^[20]
- 7) The final formulation was dried at room temperature.^[21]
- 8) The prepared face pack was stored in an airtight container.^[22]

7. EVALUTION: -

1. Organoleptic Evaluation

- Procedure: Colour, Odor, and texture were observed visually.^[23]

2. pH Determination

Procedure: 1 g sample dissolved in 10 ml distilled water and measured using pH meter.^[24]

Ideal range: 5-7

3. Particle Size Analysis

Procedure: Powder passed through sieve and uniformity checked.^[25]

4. Washability Test

Procedure: Applied on skin and washed with water to check ease of removal.^[26]

5. Skin Irritation Test

Procedure: Applied on forearm and observed for 24 hrs for irritation.^[27]

6. Stability Study

Procedure: Stored at room temperature and observed for changes.^[28]

7. Ash Value

Procedure: 2 g sample incinerated at 450–600°C and ash calculated.^[29]

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS: -

1) Organoleptic evaluation: -

Table 8.1: Organoleptic Evaluation

Batch	Colour	Odor	Texture	Result
F1	Light brown	Pleasant	Smooth	Pass
F2	Brown	Pleasant	Very smooth	Pass (best)
F3	Brownish	Mild	smooth	Pass
F4	Dark brown	Mild	Slightly coarse	Pass
F5	Light brown	mild	coarse	Fail
F6	brown	pleasant	smooth	pass

2) pH Evaluation:-

Table 8.2 pH evaluation

Batch	pH	Result
F1	5.5	Pass
F2	6.2	Pass (best)
F3	6.5	Pass
F4	6.8	Pass
F5	7.2	Fail
F6	6.9	pass

3) Particle Size:-

Table 8.3 particle size

Batch	observation	Result
F1	Uniform	Pass
F2	Fine	Pass (best)
F3	Fine	Pass
F4	Slightly coarse	Pass
F5	Coarse	Fail
F6	Uniform	pass

4) Washability test: -

Table 8.4 washability test

Batch	observation	Result
F1	Good	Pass
F2	Excellent	Pass
F3	Excellent	Pass

F4	Moderate	Pass
F5	Difficult to wash	Fail
F6	good	Pass

5) Skin Irritation test:-

Table 8.5 skin irritation test

Batch	Observation	Result
F1	No irritation	Pass
F2	No irritation	Pass (best)
F3	No irritation	Pass
F4	No irritation	Pass
F5	Mild redness	Fail
F6	No irritation	pass

6) Stability test :-

Table 8.6 stability test

Batch	observation	Result
F1	Stable	Pass
F2	Stable	Pass (best)
F3	Stable	Pass
F4	Slight change	Pass
F5	Colour change	Fail
F6	stable	Pass

7) Ash value:-

Table 8.7 Ash value

Batch	Ash (%)	Limit ($\leq 10\%$)	Result
F1	8.5	≤ 10	Pass
F2	8.0	≤ 10	Pass (best)
F3	7.5	≤ 10	Pass
F4	9.5	≤ 10	Pass
F5	10.5	≤ 10	Fail
F6	9.0	≤ 10	pass

Figure 8.1 observation

DISCUSSION:-

The herbal face pack formulations (F1–F6) were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters including organoleptic properties, pH, particle size, washability, skin irritation, stability, and ash value.

All batches showed acceptable organoleptic properties such as color, odor, and texture, except F5 which was slightly coarse. The pH of formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, and F6 was within the acceptable range (5–7), while F5 showed a higher pH and failed the test.

Particle size analysis using sieve no. 52 indicated that F2 and F3 had fine and uniform particles, whereas F5 showed coarse particles. Washability studies revealed that F2 and F3 had excellent washability, while F5 was difficult to remove.

Skin irritation test showed no irritation for all batches except F5, which produced mild redness. Stability studies confirmed that all formulations were stable except F5, which showed slight color change.

Ash value results were within acceptable limits ($\leq 10\%$) for all batches except F5.

Overall, formulations F2 and F3 passed all evaluation parameters and were found to be the most suitable formulations, whereas F5 failed due to multiple parameter deviations.

Therefore, F2 and F3 are considered as optimized herbal face pack formulation.

9. CONCLUSION

People today require a treatment for a variety of skin-related problems that does not cause adverse side effects. It is our good attempt to formulate the herbal face pack powder containing natural herbal

ingredients such as Multani Matti, Sweet potato powder, Turmeric, Rose water, sandalwood powder. after evaluation, we found good properties for the face packs powder, free from skin irritation and maintained its consistency even after stability storage conditions.

The herbal face pack was successfully formulated using natural ingredients.

Most formulations passed evaluation tests and were found safe and effective.

However, formulation F5 failed in multiple parameters, indicating improper balance of ingredients.

Thus, F2 and F3 are considered optimized formulations for safe and effective use.

therefore, F2 and F3 are considered as the best and optimized formulations.

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